

Book Review: Communicating Science: Professional, Popular, Literary

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Keywords

Book, Science Communication

Governments and scientific establishments have been encouraging the development of science communication. In this book, Nicholas Russell critically examines the origin of this drive to improve communication, and discusses why simply improving scientists' communication skills and understanding of their audiences may not be enough.

Avoiding specialist jargon, this book provides an insight into science's place in society by looking at science communication in three contexts: the professional patterns of communication among scientists, popular communication to the public, and science in literature and drama.

This three-part framework shows how historical and cultural factors operate in today's complex communication landscape, and should be actively considered when designing and evaluating science communication. Ideal for students and practitioners in science, engineering and medicine, this book provides a better understanding of the culture, sociology and mechanics of professional and popu-

lar communication. This book is a must as an academic introduction to science communication, but not necessarily a must-have on the practitioners' reading list.

Biography

Pedro Russo is the international project manager of the educational programme Universe Awareness. Until 2010 he was the Global Coordinator for the International Year of Astronomy 2009. He is a member of the Astronomy Department and Science Communication & Society Department of Leiden University, Leiden University.

Figure 1. Communicating Science: Professional, Popular, Literary
Nicholas Russell
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